

Neuropeptide S receptor (version 2019.4) in the IUPHAR/BPS Guide to Pharmacology Database

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Abstract

The neuropeptide S receptor (NPS, **provisional nomenclature [18]**) responds to the 20 amino-acid peptide neuropeptide S derived from a precursor (*NPS*, P0C0P6).

Contents

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